

Teachers' Tribune
International Journal of
Teachers and Students

Modarese Bartar Quarterly (MBQ)

International Journal of Teachers and Students

Carbon Derivative, Graphene, and its effects on Proteins and Consequences for Glioma Disease: a review

2023,1(2), 35-41

Zahra Zare

Farzanegan4, Elite Students' High school, Tabriz, Iran

Abstract

In the past few years, there has been a notable increase in the attention given to the application of graphene and graphene-based materials (GBMs) in the field of tissue engineering for the enhancement of biomaterials. Graphene oxide (GO), reduced graphene oxide (RGO), and their chemical derivatives have specifically attracted significant interest within this domain. The increased attention towards GBMs arises from their capacity to improve the advancement and effectiveness of biomaterials employed in tissue engineering. This study investigates the subsequent results by primarily relying on in vitro and in vivo evaluations of cytotoxicity and genotoxicity for materials associated with graphene. Furthermore, it offers a thorough examination of the techniques utilized to assess the toxic properties of these substances. The primary aim of this review is to offer a source of inspiration for current nanotoxicological approaches pertaining to materials based on graphene. This article investigates the impact of graphene on proteins and its consequences for glioma disease.

Keywords: *Carbon, Cancer, Glioma, Graphene, Protein*

In the realm of anticancer therapy, nanoparticles have emerged as highly valuable resources in recent times. These modern organic compounds have gained significant recognition for their potential in combating cancer. Numerous research studies have suggested that nanomaterials may hold promise in improving health outcomes, specifically in the realm of cancer therapy (Zhao et al., 2017). Nevertheless, there remains a dearth of all-encompassing comprehension and endorsement concerning their prospective advantages. For instance, there is a widespread need for information concerning the newly created substance referred to as "graphene."

Graphene, acknowledged as the thinnest material globally (Seabra et al., 2014), is a carbon allotrope. The distinguishing feature of a graphene sheet resides in its proportion of thickness to surface area, differentiating it from all other recognized nanomaterials. Graphene chips have the potential to match or even surpass the size of cells. The mobility of these entities within tissues is limited, impeding their efficient utilization by phagocytic cells. Graphene exhibits distinctive physicochemical properties. A chemical research in toxicology conducted by Seabra et al. (2014) highlights the remarkable characteristic of the rapid speed at which its electrons are in motion, leading to distinctive organic impacts on different cellular structures and tissues. Graphene possesses the potential to disturb the transportation of vital nutrients, induce stress, and activate apoptotic pathways in cancer cells, owing to its capability to interact with cell membranes by attaching and binding to cell receptors. Moreover, graphene is characterized by two dynamic constituents, i.e., surfaces and edges. It possesses the remarkable capability of forming bonds with organic atoms at its edges, whereas its surfaces exhibit the ability to adhere to cells.

Graphene and its derivatives exhibit the ability to function as nucleating agents due to their capacity to interact with proteins via hydrophobic and pi-pi stacking mechanisms. Consequently, this interaction leads to an augmentation in the concentration of proteins surrounding the targets situated on the surface of graphene and its derivatives (Garg et al., 1998).

Graphene, along with its supplementary constituents, showcases immense promise as viable candidates for essential biomedical applications owing to their exceptional versatility. The comprehensive comprehension of the potential risks linked with graphene-based materials is imperative due to their escalating usage in a conventional setting. The prevalence of nanotechnology is increasing, leading to a projected rise in the prolonged exposure of both humans and the environment to nanomaterials based on graphene. The production and use of graphene-related materials have raised concerns regarding potential risk factors, leading to a significant surge in nanotoxicological studies conducted over the past ten years (Seabra et al., 2014). The researchers have been investigating the impact of nanostructural and biological instinctive factors on different levels of organization within living systems, spanning from biomolecules to animals. They have endeavored to comprehend the impacts of these variables on the operation of biological organisms.

As previously examined (Tomczyk et al., 2020), it has been established that the distinctive physicochemical characteristics of graphene and GBMs exert a substantial influence on cellular response. The influence of the physicochemical properties of graphene on the biomolecular

characteristics of proteins has been thoroughly investigated and analyzed in distinct research studies (Aillon et al., 2009). The distinctive physicochemical features of graphene offer promising prospects for manipulating protein adsorption, presentation, modification, and ultimately determining cell fate. This is of significant importance as proteins on biomaterial surfaces have been found to play a pivotal role in influencing cell behavior for nanomaterials (Campitelli et al., 2008).

It is expected that GBMs will emerge as extremely promising biomaterials for tissue engineering usages in the foreseeable future. Hence, it is crucial to tackle the physicochemical interaction that occurs between the surface of graphene and the process of protein adsorption, protein structure, and cellular response. This is essential in order to establish an efficient interface between these materials. Conducting coordination experiments, speculations, and simulation studies enables the attainment of a thorough understanding of various scales.

In this study, our objective is to establish a correlation between the aforementioned domains and investigate the potential of manipulating the physicochemical properties of graphene in order to control cellular results through the proteins that encapsulate the graphene surface. This evaluation is anticipated to motivate a larger cohort of scholars to explore this swiftly growing subdomain. Moreover, it is expected that in the near future, a comprehensive analysis will be carried out to establish a relationship between the separate domains (GBM-protein and protein-cell) that play a role in the interaction between cellular function and the physicochemical characteristics of GBM.

In recent times, extensive research has been conducted to explore the impact of functionalized graphene materials on various living organisms. Numerous studies have provided evidence that the biodistribution and toxicity of graphene and its clearance from the body are significantly influenced by its surface chemistry and size. In vitro evaluation of the effects of graphene platelets on glioblastoma multiforme cells conducted by Jaworski, et al. (2013) highlights that living organisms can be influenced differently by distinct types of graphene materials. Most of the research has concentrated on graphene oxide, which is produced using chemical techniques. Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that there is a lack of organic investigations carried out on graphene platelets (GPs) produced using physical techniques. In essence, the authors are cognizant that these platelets are generated through the direct shedding of graphite, bypassing any initial oxidation process. The hydrophobic nature of the reduced graphene particles (GPs) stands in contrast to the graphene oxide, which demonstrates remarkable dispersion properties in water. This disparity leads to the creation of stable hydrocolloids. Given the distinctive physicochemical properties of GPs, which set them apart from other forms of graphene materials, it was postulated that GPs might display specific cellular toxicity.

Gliomas are essential brain tumors that are thought to arise from neuroglial stem or begetter cells. These tumors have historically been classified as astrocytic, oligodendroglial, or ependymal tumors based on their histological features. They have been assigned WHO grades I–IV, which represent different degrees of risk.

The favorable results obtained from our earlier investigations on the application of diamond hydrophobic nanoparticles in the treatment of glioma have shown great potential (Gómez-Aldapa

et al., 2020). Throughout the investigation, they proposed the hypothesis that GPs might also exert a detrimental impact on glioma cells. The attributes of glioma cells may vary depending on the specific cell line employed. The study utilized two separate human cell lines, i.e., U87 and U118, to conduct their research. These lines demonstrated distinct morphological properties, the impact of qualities implicated in the regulation of the cell cycle, and susceptibility to modified cellular demise. The aim of this examination was to assess the harmfulness of GPs and the pro-apoptotic and necrotic impacts of graphene on cancerous cells.

The graphene fragments demonstrated a pronounced tendency to concentrate in immediate vicinity of the cells, suggesting a predilection of the cells towards graphene. In a study investigating the impact of graphene on bacterial cells, a comparable trend was identified (Campitelli et al., 2008)

The close proximity of glioma cells to GPs is evident from the microscopic images of the cells and the self-organization of GP. Moreover; the chips were primarily associated with the cell soma rather than its protrusions. This observation exemplifies the cooperative engagement between the GPs and cells owing to their distinct chemical and/or physical attributes. Further, it demonstrated that this effect might rely on the cellular morphology, specifically the quantity and structure of protrusions.

The practicality assessment of cells unveiled an adverse impact of GPs on glioma cells. A concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ led to a survival rate of 60% in the U118 line and 54% in the U87 cells. In the examination of mortality, a comparable result was evident, as the same concentration resulted in the demise of 42% of U87 cells and 52% of U118 cells. This discovery was consistent with earlier research conducted by scientists who have proven the significant toxicity of graphene oxide (Jaworski et al., 2013). Nevertheless, there are signs suggesting that graphene oxide exhibits the toxic characteristic of Moo. Different concentrations of Moo did not result in any observable cytotoxic effects when human derived cell lines A549 and SH-SY5Y were exposed to them (Nair et al., 2016). It is crucial to consider that the cytotoxicity of GPs cannot be directly compared to the toxicity of graphene oxide due to their distinct physicochemical properties, which can result in diverse impacts on living organisms. Moreover, the uncertainties emerge when contrasting with different cell lines (A549 and SH-SY5Y) due to the contrasting morphology and functionality exhibited by these cell lines in comparison to U87 and U118 cells.

Although the toxicity of GPs in the display experiment on U87 and U118 cell lines was comparable/similar, the impact on the cell membrane was significant. The LDH test revealed notable disparities in the films' integrity of the two glioma cell lines after treatment with GPs. In a concentration of Moo GP, it was observed that the level of disruption in layer judgment was more pronounced in U87 cells when compared to U118 cells. The morphology of the cell lines may offer elucidation in this matter. The U118 cells demonstrate a greater level of surface branching in comparison to the U87 cells. As a result, the U118 cell layer exhibited a greater length, accompanied by a higher degree of projections towards the central body of the cells (Aillon et al., 2009). Moreover, the observation of the bio-interactions between GPs and the cells demonstrated that the GPs displayed a heightened preference for the cellular body as opposed to the projections. The elucidation of the toxic property component could be achieved through the examination of the cell film surface. As a result of the greater number of branches observed in U118 cells in

comparison to U87 cells, a reduced fraction of the central body surface of U118 cells remained unexposed. As a result, the GPs would have only impacted a reduced portion of the overall cell layer. Additionally, there were significant variations observed in the distribution and arrangement of receptors and subcellular organelles within the central body and bulges across different cell lines. These variations have the potential to alter the biological effects of the GPs (Jaworski et al., 2013).

The initial and subsequent inquiry was carried out to illustrate the fundamental atomic constituents implied in the interaction between GPs and cells (Breindel et al., 2019). The conducted discoveries suggest that the toxicity of GPs may primarily stem from the interaction between GPs and U87 and U118 cell layers. The morphological characteristics of various glioma cells, the atomic state of cell lines, and the concentration of GP can potentially influence the organic response of glioma cells to GPs. The findings indicate that the toxicity of GPs towards glioma cells escalates as the concentrations of GPs elevate from 10 to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Nevertheless, GPs exclusively initiate programmed cell death (apoptosis) in the U118 cell line, without eliciting necrosis or cellular decay. This observation highlighted the promising potential of GPs as a viable therapeutic option for cancer treatment (Jarosz et al., 2016).

Further exploration is necessary to accelerate the clinical usages of graphene-based cancer therapeutics. Crucial aspects that require examination include the impact of modified graphene oxide (GO) on drug-loading and controlled-release, the internalization mechanism of polyethylene glycol (PGD), the in vivo biocompatibility of PGD, and the significant pathway of PGD inducing glioma cell apoptosis. These areas of study are essential for enhancing our understanding and utilization of graphene-based cancer treatments.

To summarize, this synopsis underscores the detrimental impacts of graphene on ecological systems, thereby characterizing them as imprudent endeavors. Additional research is required to explore the harmful effects of materials derived from graphene and establish an authentic connection between their chemical, structural, and morphological characteristics and the environmental consequences. This involves examining a variety of manufactured and manipulated results. Graphene-derived substances possess the capability to ensure the secure application of this versatile textile through the provision of pertinent data. It is recommended to carry out the future research on the impact of graphene and other carbon derivatives on cancer cells and glioma and consider the attributes of the proteins comprising cancerous tumors.

References

1. Aillon, K. L., Xie, Y., El-Gendy, N., Berkland, C. J., & Forrest, M. L. (2009). Effects of nanomaterial physicochemical properties on in vivo toxicity. *Advanced drug delivery reviews*, 61(6), 457-466.
2. Breindel, L., Burz, D. S., & Shekhtman, A. (2019). Interaction proteomics by using in-cell NMR spectroscopy. *Journal of proteomics*, 191, 202-211.
3. Campitelli, P., & Ceppi, S. (2008). Effects of composting technologies on the chemical and physicochemical properties of humic acids. *Geoderma*, 144(1-2), 325-333.
4. Garg, A., & Sinnott, S. B. (1998). Effect of chemical functionalization on the mechanical properties of carbon nanotubes. *Chemical Physics Letters*, 295(4), 273-278.
5. Gómez-Aldapa, C. A., Velazquez, G., Gutierrez, M. C., Rangel-Vargas, E., Castro-Rosas, J., & Aguirre-Loredo, R. Y. (2020). Effect of polyvinyl alcohol on the physicochemical properties of biodegradable starch films. *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 239, 122027.
6. Jarosz, A., Skoda, M., Dudek, I., & Szukiewicz, D. (2016). Oxidative stress and mitochondrial activation as the main mechanisms underlying graphene toxicity against human cancer cells. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*, 2016.
7. Jaworski, S., Sawosz, E., Grodzik, M., Winnicka, A., Prasek, M., Wierzbicki, M., & Chwalibog, A. (2013). In vitro evaluation of the effects of graphene platelets on glioblastoma multiforme cells. *International journal of nanomedicine*, 413-420.
8. Kumar, S., & Parekh, S. H. (2020). Linking graphene-based material physicochemical properties with molecular adsorption, structure and cell fate. *Communications Chemistry*, 3(1), 8.
9. Nair, J. J., Van Staden, J., & Bastida, J. (2016). Cytotoxic alkaloid constituents of the Amaryllidaceae. *Studies in natural products chemistry*, 49, 107-156.
10. Seabra, A. B., Paula, A. J., de Lima, R., Alves, O. L., & Durán, N. (2014). Nanotoxicity of graphene and graphene oxide. *Chemical research in toxicology*, 27(2), 159-168.

11. Tomczyk, A., Sokołowska, Z., & Boguta, P. (2020). Biochar physicochemical properties: pyrolysis temperature and feedstock kind effects. *Reviews in Environmental Science and Bio/Technology*, 19, 191-215.

12. Zhao, S. X., Ta, N., & Wang, X. D. (2017). Effect of temperature on the structural and physicochemical properties of biochar with apple tree branches as feedstock material. *Energies*, 10(9), 1293.